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A REVIEW ON SOLID DISPERSIONS DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Solid dispersions have attracted considerable interest as an efficient means of improving the dissolution rate and hence the bioavailability of a range of hydrophobic drugs. This article reviews the various preparation techniques for solid dispersion. The different types of solid dispersions based on the molecular arrangement have been highlighted. An ideal drug delivery system should be able to deliver an adequate amount of drug, preferably for an extended period of time for its optimum therapeutic activity. Most drugs are inherently not long lasting in the body and require multiple daily dosing to achieve the desired blood concentration to produce therapeutic activity. To overcome such problem, controlled release and sustained release delivery systems are receiving considerable attention from pharmaceutical industries worldwide. A controlled release drug delivery system not only prolongs the duration of action, but also results in predictable and reproducible drug-release kinetics. One advantage of controlled release dosage forms is enhanced patient compliance. Drug delivery systems based on the principles of solid dispersion (1). The enhancement of oral bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs remains one of the most challenging aspects of drug development

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INTRODUCTION

Poor aqueous solubility and bioavailability of drugs into the body after administration are two prime issues which are faced by the pharmaceutical industry at the present time. This problem has been the major problem hampering the release of new chemical entities into the market. Every year more than 50% of the potentially active pharmaceutical ingredients get rejected due to the above stated problems [1]. During the last decade, more than 40% of the new chemical entities launched in the U.S. pharmaceutical market faced the problem of adequate aqueous solubility [2]. Therefore, pharmaceutical companies are focusing on finding a method or technology by which they can enhance the aqueous solubility and bioavailability of the drug. To date, various methods for modification of active pharmaceutical ingredients have included physical, chemical and controlled solid state methods[3]. Each of the methods given above has their own drawbacks which restrain their use to modify the active pharmaceutical ingredient to improve its aqueous solubility and bioavailability[3]. Some other conventional methods used to improve aqueous solubility and bioavailability include: the use of surfactants[4]; pH modification [5, 6]; solid dispersion technique[7, 8]; cosolvent and hydrotrop formation[9]; co-crystallization techniques[5, 10]; and many more.

An ideal drug delivery system should be able to deliver an adequate amount of drug, preferably for an extended period of time for its optimum therapeutic activity. Most drugs are inherently not long lasting in the body and require multiple daily dosing to achieve the desired blood concentration to produce therapeutic activity. To overcome such problem, controlled release and sustained release delivery systems are receiving considerable attention from pharmaceutical industries worldwide. A controlled release drug delivery system not only prolongs the duration of action, but also results in predictable and reproducible drug-release kinetics. One advantage of controlled release dosage forms is enhanced patient compliance. Drug delivery systems based on the principles of solid dispersion (1). The enhancement of oral bioavailability of poorly

water soluble drugs remains one of the most challenging aspects of drug development. As **Figure 1** indicates that salt formation, solubilization, and particle size reduction have commonly been used to increase dissolution rate and thereby oral absorption and bioavailability of such drugs, there are practical limitations of these techniques. The salt formation is not feasible for neutral compounds and the synthesis of appropriate salt forms of drugs that are weakly acidic or weakly basic may often not be practical. Even when salts can be prepared, an increased dissolution rate in the gastrointestinal tract may not be achieved in many cases because of the reconversion of salts into aggregates of their respective acid or base forms. The solubilization of drugs in organic solvents or in aqueous media by the use of surfactants and cosolvents leads to liquid formulations that are usually undesirable from the viewpoints of patient acceptability and commercialization. Although particle size reduction is commonly used to increase dissolution rate, there is a practical limit to how much size reduction can be achieved by such commonly used methods as controlled crystallization, grinding, etc. The use of very fine powders in a dosage form may also be problematic because of handling difficulties and poor wettability. Much of the research that has been reported on solid dispersion technologies involves drugs that are poorly water-soluble and highly permeable to biological membranes as with these drugs dissolution is the rate limiting step to absorption. Hence, the hypothesis has been that the rate of absorption in vivo will be concurrently accelerated with an increase in the rate of drug dissolution. In the Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) (**Figure 2**) drugs with low aqueous solubility and high membrane permeability are categorized as Class II drugs (2). Therefore, solid dispersion technologies are particularly promising for improving the oral absorption and bioavailability of BCS Class II drugs.

Oral drug delivery is the simplest and easiest way of administering drugs (3). Because of the greater stability, smaller bulk, accurate dosage and easy production, solid oral dosages forms have many advantages over other types of oral

dosage forms. Therefore, most of the new chemical entities (NCE) under development these days are intended to be used as a solid dosage form that originate an effective and reproducible *in vivo* plasma concentration after oral administration (4, 5). In fact, most NCEs are poorly water soluble drugs, not well-absorbed after oral administration, which can detract from the drug's inherent efficacy (6, 7). Moreover, most promising NCEs, despite their high permeability, are generally only absorbed in the upper small intestine, absorption being reduced significantly after the ileum, showing, therefore, that there is a small absorption window (8, 9). Consequently, if these drugs are not completely released in this gastrointestinal area, they will have a low bioavailability. Therefore, one of the major current challenges of the pharmaceutical industry is related to strategies that improve the water solubility of drugs (10). Drug release is a crucial and limiting step for oral drug bioavailability, particularly for drugs with low gastrointestinal solubility and high permeability. By improving the drug release profile of these drugs, it is possible to enhance their bioavailability and reduce side effects. Solid dispersions are one of the most successful strategies to improve drug release of poorly soluble drugs. These can be defined as molecular mixtures of poorly water soluble drugs in hydrophilic carriers, which present a drug release profile that is driven by the polymer properties.

In addition to the improvement of bioavailability, most of recent researches on solid dispersion systems have been being directed toward their application to the development of extended-release dosage forms. However several factors such as complicated preparation method, low reproducibility of physicochemical properties, difficulty of formulation development and scale-up and physical instability for solid dispersion make it difficult to apply the systems to solid dispersion dosage forms. Especially in order to maintain a supersaturation level of drug for an extended time, re-crystallization of drug must be prevented during its release from dosage form (11). Dissolution retardation through the solid

dispersion technique has become a field of interest in recent year. Shaikh et al prepared prolonged release solid dispersions of acetaminophen and theophylline by a simple evaporation method using ethyl cellulose as water-insoluble carrier. (12). Oral devices made to be retained in the stomach for a long time and to ensure slow delivery of drug above it's absorption site, could provide increased and more reproducible drug bioavailability (13). During the last decade, the sustained release technique has been largely utilized to obtain the controlled release of pharmaceutical forms of both water soluble and sparingly soluble drugs using hydrophobic and hydrophilic polymers, respectively. Limitations in the development of solid dispersions were mainly due to physical instability of these systems. During this time phase separation of components can occur. Furthermore, polymeric materials are not in thermodynamic equilibrium below their glass transition temperatures (T_g), so the solid polymer approaches its more stable state (lower energy). If these macromolecular rearrangements occur during the experiments, a variation of the mechanical and permeation properties of the materials can be observed. This process is known as 'Physical ageing' (14).

The absorption of drugs from a solid dosage form, when taken orally, can be divided into two steps - (1) the process of dissolution of the drug *in vivo* which leads to a solution; and (2) the transport of the dissolved drug from the solution across the gastrointestinal membrane. Each step involved in the process of absorption of the drug is very crucial. The overall absorption and bioavailability of the drug may be affected by the poor performance of either step mentioned above[1]. From among the many new active pharmaceutical ingredients introduced into the market, almost all the active pharmaceutical ingredients face the problem enumerated above. Either step one or two may lead to a decrease in overall bioavailability of the active pharmaceutical ingredient. Biopharmaceutical Classification (BCS) system [2] classifies these active pharmaceutical ingredients into four classes as given below:

Figure 1: Approaches to Increase solubility/ Dissolution

Figure 2: Biopharmaceutical Classification System break down of the pharma new chemical entity pipeline

Class I – High permeability, High Solubility. Compounds of this class are well absorbed and the absorption rate for these compounds is greater than the rate of excretion.

Class II – High Permeability, Low Solubility. Compounds of this class have poor bioavailability because their rate of solvation is very low.

Class III – Low Permeability, High Solubility. Compounds of this class have poor bioavailability because their permeation rate is very low.

Class IV – Low Permeability, Low Solubility. Compounds of this class have poor bioavailability because of both low solubility and absorption which limits its permeation rate.

Fincher extensively studied the relationship between the particle size of drugs, their dissolution rates and their bioavailability [3]. According to Fincher, the majority of the poorly water-soluble drugs show poor bioavailability due to the poor rate of dissolution, which is further dependent on the surface area of the drug particle available for dissolution [3]. Therefore, the dissolution rate can be enhanced by increasing the surface area. This can be achieved by the process of particle size reduction.

Particle size reduction of the active pharmaceutical agent can be achieved by: (1) trituration and grinding; (2) ball milling; (3) fluid energy micronization; (4) precipitation under controlled condition which is achieved by changing solvents or temperature, by using ultrasonic waves[4] or spray drying[5]; and (5) using gastric fluid to precipitate the drug in the form of fine particles[6]. The above mentioned methods are able to easily achieve the reduction in particle size. However, the dissolution rate and

absorption may not be increased due to the formation of aggregates and/or agglomerates among the fine particles which can be caused by increased surface energy and stronger Van der Waals interactions. Moreover, the fine drug particles may also have a wettability problem in water, which may lead to a poor dissolution rate[7].

A unique technique known as solid dispersion was introduced by Sekiguchi and Obi[8] in 1961 to reduce the particle size of the drug and increase the dissolution rate and rate of absorption. The first solid dispersion was developed using sulfathiazole (a poorly water soluble drug) and urea (water soluble and physiologically inert) as a carrier to increase the dissolution rate and rate of absorption by reduction in particle size. The technique used in the preparation of the solid dispersion of sulfathiazole with urea as a carrier included melting the physical mixture to a high temperature followed by rapid solidification. The drug in solid dispersion form was considered to be released as fine and dispersed particles when they come in contact with aqueous fluid. Levy[6] and Kanig[9], who worked with a number of drugs using mannitol as a carrier introduced the term solid-solid solution. Chiou and Niazi[10] performed the experiment with sulfathiazole and urea and reported that the fused mixture of sulfathiazole and urea showed an increase in dissolution rates by forming an "amorphous precipitate" or "solid solution". In solid solutions the drug is considered to be dispersed in a soluble carrier. Tachibana and Nakamura[12] first introduced a new method of preparing a solid dispersion known as the solvent evaporation method. In this method they first dispersed β -carotene in a water-soluble polymer (polyvinylpyrrolidone). They then dissolved both chemicals in a common solvent and finally completely evaporated the solvent.

According to Chiou and Riegelman[11] a solid dispersion is defined as "the dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inert carrier or matrix in solid state prepared by melting (fusion), using a solvent or a melting-solvent method." The modern definition has broadened the concept to include certain terms such as co-precipitates, nano-particles, microcapsules,

microspheres and other dispersions of drugs in polymers (carrier) prepared by using the above mentioned methods. Although the main goal of most solid dispersions is to increase the dissolution rate, this new broadened concept of a solid dispersion also has the aim of achieving goals such as altered solid-state properties, sustained release of drugs, enhanced release of drugs from ointment and suppository bases and improved stability[13].

The process of dissolution of a drug from solid dispersion includes three steps: (1) interaction of a co-precipitate with water in its vicinity; (2) the finely dispersed drug particle in the matrix structure is released; and (3) supersaturation of the solubilized drug in the diffusion layer[14].

ADVANTAGES OF SOLID DISPERSION

1. Particles with reduced particle size

Molecular dispersions, as solid dispersions, represent the last state on particle size reduction, and after carrier dissolution the drug is molecularly dispersed in the dissolution medium. Solid dispersions apply this principle to drug release by creating a mixture of a poorly water soluble drug and highly soluble carriers (Leuner and Dressman, 2000). A high surface area is formed, resulting in an increased dissolution rate and, consequently, improved bioavailability (Leuner and Dressman, 2000. and Kang *et al.* 2004).

2. Particles with improved wettability

A strong contribution to the enhancement of drug solubility is related to the drug wettability improvement verified in solid dispersions (Karavas *et al.*, 2006). It was observed that even carriers without any surface activity, such as urea (Sekiguchi and Obi, 1964) improved drug wettability. Carriers with surface activity, such as cholic acid and bile salts. When used, can significantly increase the wettability property of drug. Moreover, carriers can influence the drug dissolution profile by direct dissolution or co-solvent effects (Pouton, 2006 and Kang *et al.*, 2004).

3. Particles with higher porosity

Particles in solid dispersions have been found to have a higher degree of porosity

(Vasconcelos and Costa, 2007). The increase in porosity also depends on the carrier properties; for instance, solid dispersions containing linear polymers produce larger and more porous particles than those containing reticular polymers and, therefore, result in a higher dissolution rate (Ghaderi *et al.*, 1999). The increased porosity of solid dispersion particles also hastens the drug release profile.

4. Drugs in amorphous state

Poorly water soluble crystalline drugs, when in the amorphous state tend to have higher solubility (Pokharkar *et al.*, 2006 and Lloyd *et al.*, 1999). The enhancement of drug release can usually be achieved using the drug in its amorphous state, because no energy is required to break up the crystal lattice during the dissolution process (Taylor and Zografi, 1997). In solid dispersions, drugs are presented as supersaturated solutions after system dissolution, and it is speculated that, if drugs precipitate, it is as a metastable polymorphic form with higher solubility than the most stable crystal form (Leuner and Dressman, 2000, Karavas *et al.*, 2006).

For drugs with low crystal energy (low melting temperature or heat of fusion), the amorphous composition is primarily dictated by the difference in melting temperature between drug and carrier. For drugs with high crystal energy, higher amorphous compositions can be obtained by choosing carriers, which exhibit specific interactions with them (Vippagunta *et al.*, 2002).

DISADVANTAGES OF SOLID DISPERSION

Despite extensive expertise with solid dispersions, they are not broadly used in commercial products, mainly because there is the possibility that during processing (mechanical stress) or storage (temperature and humidity stress) the amorphous state may undergo crystallization and dissolution rate decrease with ageing. The effect of moisture on the storage stability of amorphous pharmaceuticals is also a significant concern, because it may increase drug mobility and promote drug crystallization (18). Moreover, most of the polymers used in solid dispersions can absorb moisture, which may result in phase separation, crystal growth or conversion from the amorphous to the crystalline state or

from a metastable crystalline form to a more stable structure during storage. This may result in decreased solubility and dissolution rate. Therefore, exploitation of the full potential of amorphous solids requires their stabilization in solid state, as well as during in vivo performance (19).

LIMITATIONS OF SOLID DISPERSION SYSTEMS

Limitations of this technology have been a drawback for the commercialization of solid dispersions. The limitations include:

1. Laborious and expensive methods of preparation,
2. Reproducibility of physicochemical characteristics,
3. Difficulty in incorporating into formulation of dosage forms,
4. Scale-up of manufacturing process, and
5. Stability of the drug and vehicle.
6. Its method of preparation,

Various methods have been tried recently to overcome the limitation and make the preparation practically feasible. Some of the suggested approaches to overcome the aforementioned problems and lead to industrial scale production are discussed here under alternative strategies.

SUITABLE PROPERTIES OF A CARRIER FOR SOLID DISPERSIONS

Following criteria should be considered during selection of carriers: (a) High water solubility – improve wettability and enhance dissolution (b) High glass transition point – improve stability (c) Minimal water uptake (reduces T_g) (d) Soluble in common solvent with drug –solvent evaporation (e) Relatively low melting point –melting process (f) Capable of forming a solid solution with the drug-similar solubility parameters

First generation carriers

Crystalline carriers: Urea, Sugars, Organic acids

Second generation carriers

Amorphous carriers: Polyethyleneglycol, Povidone, Polyvinylacetate, Polymethacrylate, cellulose derivatives

Third generation carriers

Surface active self emulsifying carriers:
Poloxamer 408, Tween 80, Gelucire 44/14.

SOLVENT SELECTION FOR SOLID DISPERSION SYSTEMS

In order to prepare solid dispersion, solvents should be selected on the basis of following criteria: (a) Dissolve both drug and carrier (b) Toxic solvents to be avoided due to the risk of residual levels after preparation e.g. chloroform and dichloromethane (c) Ethanol is a less toxic alternative (d) Water based systems preferable (e) Use of surfactants to create carrier drug solutions but care should be taken as they can reduce the glass transition point.

Class I Solvents (Solvents to be avoided)

Solvents in Class I should not be employed in the manufacture of drug substances, excipients and drug products because of their deleterious environmental effect.

Class II Solvents (Solvents to be limited)

Solvents in Class II should be limited in pharmaceutical products because of their inherent toxicity.

Class III Solvents (Solvents with low toxic potential)

Solvents in class III may be regarded as less toxic and of lower risk to human health. Class III includes no solvents known as a human health hazard at level normally accepted in pharmaceuticals.

Class IV Solvents (Solvents for which no adequate toxicological data was found)

Some solvents may also be of interest to manufacturers of excipients, drug substances, or drug products for example Petroleum ether, isopropyl ether. However, no adequate

toxicological data on which to base a PDE was found.

Classification of Solid dispersions

In 1971, Chiou and Riegelmann[11] classified solid dispersions into six major categories as given below –

- (1) Simple eutectic mixtures
- (2) Solid solutions
- (3) Glass solutions and glass suspensions
- (4) Amorphous precipitations of a drug in a crystalline matrix
- (5) Compound or complex formation between the drug and the carrier
- (6) Any combinations of the above groups

GENERAL METHOD OF PREPARATION

Various preparation methods for solid dispersions have been reported in literature. These methods deal with the challenge of mixing a matrix and a drug, preferably on a molecular level (**Figure 3**), while matrix and drug are generally poorly miscible. During many of the preparation techniques, de-mixing (partially or complete), and formation of different phases is observed. Phase separations like crystallization or formation of amorphous drug clusters are difficult to control and therefore unwanted. It was already recognized in one of the first studies on solid dispersions that the extent of phase separation can be minimized by a rapid cooling procedure (20). Generally, phase separation can be prevented by maintaining a low molecular mobility of matrix and drug during preparation. On the other hand, phase separation is prevented by maintaining the driving force for phase separation low for example by keeping the mixture at an elevated temperature thereby maintaining sufficient miscibility for as long as possible. Techniques for preparation of solid dispersions (**Figure 4**) are as follows:

Figure 3: Solid State Solid Dispersions

Figure 4: Methods of preparation of Solid Dispersion

MARKETED PRODUCTS OF SOLID DISPERSIONS

S. No	Product	Technology
01	Rezulin	Extrusion
02	Trocetrapib	Spray Drying
03	Sporanox	Spray Dry Onto Substrate

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